

WASTE DUMP IDENTIFICATION BY SEMANTIC SEGMENTATION USING DEEP LEARNING AND SENTINEL 2

George Boldeanu, Teodora Selea, Fredrik Samujel Nistor, Mihaela Violeta Gheorghe

GMV Innovating Solutions Romania

ABSTRACT

Increase in total amount of waste produced at global level has serious ecosystem implications, from health risks for individuals to environmental damage. This increase is directly correlated with the urban development in the past decades, increase in consumption of goods and services or in large industrial activities. In EMERITUS project, we aim to support waste management activities with the help of Earth Observation (EO) driven products derived from Sentinel 2 using deep learning segmentation approaches. To achieve a segmentation model that can properly identify waste dumps, where training datasets are missing, manual labelling and various models testing was implied. Using tools such as Optuna, a more straightforward approach is used for hyperparameters search. It is observed that the proposed model identifies waste dumps locations in different Sentinel 2 tiles, with main false positives in areas with very high spectral mixing (e.g. parking lots).

Index Terms— Waste dumps detection, Deep Learning, Semantic Segmentation

1. INTRODUCTION

Global population reached the 8 billion mark in 2022, increasing over 4 times in the last 100 years. With this growth, impact on the environment increases accordingly. One of the factors that increase the environmental pressure is the waste creation, with some forecasts that put the estimates of global waste production at around 3.4 billion tons by 2040 [1]. At EU level, in the year 2020, waste production was around 4.808 kg/capita, from which 505 kg was classified as municipal waste [2]. Even with strong regulations and directives that implement different approaches when it comes to waste disposal, environmental crimes appear, with both managed waste dump sites and illegal ones.

Also, poorly managed dumps can cause infiltration of leachate and other heavy metals into aquifers and can lead to contamination of water sources.

EO is a very suitable data source to improve detection and monitoring of various waste dumps locations where traditional methods will imply very high costs. In terms of big data analysis, Deep Learning (DL) has become in the recent decade one of the hot and most fast-growing topics.

Even if neural networks were ignored for a long period, recent advances in Computer Vision algorithms, bigger labelled training datasets and development of GPU systems allowed more complex tasks to be executed with the help of DL. DL use in field of EO is suitable for various tasks, from object identification to segmentation or scene classification. To name a few real-world cases: ships identification and tracking, Land Use/Land Cover mapping, water mapping, biophysical indices calculation etc.

Usually, as far as 2023, DL models use more VHR EO data (from satellites/UAV/aerial) and more less medium multispectral EO, such as Landsat 8/9 or Sentinel-2 [3]. Most of available benchmarks for EO DL applications are formed from aerial RGB images (16 benchmarks) and only few from multispectral imagery.

When it comes to use DL and EO data to identify waste dumps some progress was made, but most studies rely on very high-resolution imagery such as Geo-Eye and Worldview [4, 5] or even UAV imagery [6]. Sentinel-2 was used into an attempt to classify plastic waste in Southeast Asia using a patch classifier with good results [7].

Due to its high availability and temporal resolution, free data such as Sentinel-2 would offer valuable insights for preventing waste related environmental crimes and obtaining a realistic assessment of the current global situation. Also, the use of Sentinel-2 in a task like identifying and monitoring waste dumps can reduce the gap when it comes to developing countries where high resolution data at higher temporal interval is rather expensive. Therefore, the need for DL applications that rely on multispectral imagery is not only desirable, but necessary to make the best use out of open medium resolution data.

In this study our proposal consist in the implementation of a DL approach that use some of the best performing semantic segmentation models (SS) to identify waste dumps. For identification of waste dumps, SS are the most suitable choice because of the smaller time required to annotate data for training and due to the fact that an instance segmentation task was irrelevant (the object count it's not important). The study area will represent the national territory of Romania.

2. DATA

The first problematic in fulfilling the objective was the lack of training data. For the SS approach the need for

precise masks is essentially, but their availability is very scarce, sometimes inexistent. Almost all SS in EO is focused on Land Use Land Cover (LULC) applications and use general datasets with variable number of classes, such as: Corine Land Cover, ESA World Cover 10m, NLCD etc. [8] for training their models. Also, there are approaches that propose their own labelled data for SS tasks such as Dynamic World [9].

The task of identifying and monitoring waste dump sites posed challenges that necessitated the creation of our own labeled dataset. This was due to the absence of trustworthy open-source datasets encompassing masks specifically tailored for this purpose. One approach was to use CLC 132 class, correspondent for dump sites, but this approach proved to be without results because of the poor accuracy of the dataset. There were identified issues with the vectors, mostly wrong areas classified as dump, as well as a very small number of vectors for the territory of Romania (11 vectors designating waste dumps).

To address the lack of SS masks, manual vectorization was employed. This consisted in identification of waste dumps using both VHR Google Satellite WMS service from QGIS and Sentinel 2. When a potential site was identified on VHR, the presence of the dump was verified with Sentinel 2 and the mask was created accordingly to its extent at the date of the Sentinel-2 acquisition. Identifying waste dump locations was done for 2021 and 2022, from May till October for Romanian territory (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Waste dumps sites across Romania

Because the projects aimed in identifying and monitoring both legal and illegal waste dumps, the created masks were categorized as administered and unadministered (Table 1). In this matter administered means that the aspect of the waste dump is homogenous and has a regular form that represent some form of organization (legal or not) and unadministered is a reference to those that are sporadic, heterogeneous and with unregular shape. Sentinel 2 data was downloaded from Creodias Explorer with variable cloud cover to cover cloudy and clear scenarios, all around the year to cover as much as seasonal variability of waste dumps and background data. Also, data for year 2021 and

2022 was downloaded in a total of 34 of tiles and 59 images to cover inter seasonality of waste dumps and background data.

Table 1. Mask distribution over years and form of administration

Class	Number of masks	
	2021	2022
Administered	52	71
Unadministered	149	232

The total number of the training dataset consisted of 4024 combinations of images and masks patches (with 128x128 dimensions) which ensured the greatest spatio-temporal variability and cloud cover diversity. This data was divided in 70% for training, 15% for validation and 15% for testing. The training, validation and testing dataset consisted of images with variable cloud cover and covering all the existing dates with a random subsampling criteria.

3. METHODS

To find the most appropriate DL model for the task of SS in this case, a series of state-of-the-art (SOTA) segmentation models were tested. Also, along with those models some feature extractors were proposed as encoders. The selected feature extractors are based on Squeeze and Excitation-ResNeXt which are ResNeXt blocks with added Squeeze and Excitation module [10] and on ResNeSt block which includes a split-attention block for each cardinality [11]. For testing which combination of model encoder was most fitted for the task, Optuna framework was employed. Optuna is a framework that searches for the optimal hyperparameters and is not constricted by the framework where is it deployed: PyTorch, TensorFlow, Keras etc. It has an intuitive code structure and object-based orientation which makes it suitable for identifying the values to be used in finetuning the hyperparameters [12]. Besides hyperparameters like learning rate, optimizer or loss function, Optuna was employed to identify the optimal encoder. For example, for each model a list of potential encoders was set and tests were run for 10 epochs on 100 trials.

Optuna trials concluded that the most suitable combination was the pair formed from ResNeSt101 and DeepLabV3+. Also, as hyperparameters the best optimizer was Adam with a learning rate of 0.00014130. The Tversky Focal Loss (TFL) was the most suitable loss function due to the nature of the training dataset. The training dataset is a very high imbalanced dataset, where an approximate of 24 images with background corresponded to 1 image with waste dump in it, or more than 99% of the total pixels were part of the background class. For an imbalanced dataset case, TFL is specially designed, but also has additional parameters like alpha, beta and gamma to control the classes

predictions. Alpha is a weight constant that penalizes the model for false positives (FP), beta is a weight constant that penalizes the model for false negative (FN) and gamma is a constant that squares the error function. For our combination, the best suitable values were 0.8 for alpha parameter, 0.2 for beta parameter and 2 for gamma parameter, in which the models kept the number of false identifications at a low value and with gamma value of 2 the model focuses more on harder examples.

Sentinel 2 data was stacked using all the relevant 10 and 20 meters resolution bands which were upsampled to 10 meters using bilinear interpolation method. Because red edge bands share some spectral range, an analysis of the spectral ranges was made in figure 2. First distribution plot from figure 2 represents pixels distribution for band 2 (blue channel) of the whole image dataset that contain waste dumps, as it can be seen the distribution of pixels for dumps and background are in different ranges of values. The second distribution plot from Figure 2 is for band 5 (red-edge 1) and represents the opposite behavior where the pixels for dump and background share same distribution over reflectance range. Therefore, in the Dataloader a band selection part is added and stacked data is filtered only for the 2,3,4,8,11,12 bands that will be used in training of the model.

Figure 2. Pixel range distribution over band 2 and band 5 for dumps and background

To increase the number of waste dumps locations that the model will be trained on, data augmentation was implemented with the help of Albumentations python

library. Because of the nature of the EO data, non-alteration augmentations were implemented. Those augmentations that were implemented in the Dataloader are one HorizontalFlip, one RandomRotate and one Transpose that will enrich the training dataset.

All the training was performed using PyTorch, Pytorch-Lightning and Segmentation Models libraries along with python 3.10.6.

4. RESULTS

During the training process, only data pertaining to administrated waste dumps were taken into consideration for the purpose of creating the input masks. This decision was based on the observation that legal dumps, which tend to be larger in size and have distinct homogeneous shapes, can be more easily identified in medium resolution images unlike illegal dumping, which is usually characterized by less homogeneity and more shape variations. After training the DeepLabV3+ with ResNeSt101 as encoder for 140 epochs, a validation IOU (Intersection Over Union, which is a valuable metric that assess the intersection percentage of the ground truth data with the predicted data) score of 0.6 was obtained with a testing IOU of 0.5. Those values for IOU are satisfactory, showing more than 50% intersection between predicted masks and ground truth masks. As the precision of the model remained the same on the validation and the testing dataset with a value of 0.8, the recall values were different on the validation and testing, 0.78 and 0.5, respectively. The smaller recall value on the testing set is since the FTL loss was pushed to be more focused on the limitation of the false positive cases in order to not have at least number of false identifications as dumps.

In Figure 3 are a few examples of True Positives (TP) examples with yellow and False Positives (FP) with red. FP cases are typically identified in highly spectral mixed areas, like parking lots, buildings or commercial places. Additionally, presence of dried lake beds in certain regions introduces further confusion to the model.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The lack of proper masks for SS of more diverse segmentation tasks, such as waste dumps identification, represents a time-consuming problem. This issue should be address by more standardized approaches and willingness to make datasets of different masks free and open.

Tversky Focal Loss is a reliable loss function when it comes to highly imbalanced datasets, with auxiliary parameters that can handle the True Positive/False Negative penalization of the model, which results in a more reliable model. The utilization of DeepLabV3+ with ResNeSt101, employing the resolution of Sentinel 2 imagery, yields superior outcomes compared to the models employed by [4] that were trained using Worldview and GeoEye images. However, the model's performance suffers in scenarios where the training data consists of illegal waste dump sites.

Figure 3. Inference results on different dates from a Sentinel 2 tile in Romania

This limitation arises due to the inadequate spatial resolution of Sentinel 2 data and the inherent lack of structure and homogeneity in illegal waste dumps. To address this issue, a Super Resolution model will be employed to enhance the spatial resolution of Sentinel 2 data specifically for the task of identifying small waste dumps. Subsequently, the same model will be applied for further analysis.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was sustained through the EMERITUS project. EMERITUS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101073874.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kaza, Silpa. *What a Waste 2.0: A Global Snapshot of Solid Waste Management to 2050*. Washington, DC: World Bank Group, 2018.
- [2] Eurostat. "Waste Statistics.", 2022.
- [3] Dimitrovski, Ivica, Ivan Kitanovski, Dragi Kocev, and Nikola Simidjievski. "Current Trends in Deep Learning for Earth Observation: An Open-Source Benchmark Arena for Image Classification." *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 197:18–35.n [doi: 10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2023.01.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2023.01.014), 2023.

[4] Rajkumar, Anupama, Tamas Sziranyi, Andras Majdik "Detecting Landfills Using Multi-Spectral Satellite Images and Deep Learning Methods." "The Tenth International Conference on Learning Representations 2022(ICLR,2022)", 2022.

[5] Sun, Xian, Dongshuo Yin, Fei Qin, Hongfeng Yu, Wanxuan Lu, Fanglong Yao, Qibin He, Xingliang Huang, Zhiyuan Yan, Peijin Wang, Chubo Deng, Nayu Liu, Yiran Yang, Wei Liang, Ruiping Wang, Cheng Wang, Naoto Yokoya, Ronny Hänsch, and Kun Fu. "Revealing Influencing Factors on Global Waste Distribution via Deep-Learning Based Dumpsite Detection from Satellite Imagery." *Nature Communications* 14(1):1444. [doi: 10.1038/s41467-023-37136-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-37136-1), 2023.

[6] Youme, Ousmane, Theophile Bayet, Jean Marie Dembele, and Christophe Cambier. "Deep Learning and Remote Sensing: Detection of Dumping Waste Using UAV." *Procedia Computer Science* 185:361–69. [doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2021.05.037](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.05.037), 2021.

[7] Kruse, Caleb, Edward Boyda, Sully Chen, Krishna Karra, Tristan Bou-Nahra, Dan Hammer, Jennifer Mathis, Taylor Maddalene, Jenna Jambeck, and Fabien Laurier. "Satellite Monitoring of Terrestrial Plastic Waste" edited by B. K. Veettil. *PLOS ONE* 18(1):e0278997. [doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0278997](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0278997), 2023.

[8] Tzpekenlis, Anastasios, Konstantinos Marthoglou, and Nikos Grammalidis. "Efficient Deep Semantic Segmentation for Land Cover Classification Using Sentinel Imagery." *Remote Sensing* 15(8):2027. [doi: 10.3390/rs15082027](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15082027), 2023.

[9] Brown, Christopher F., Steven P. Brumby, Brookie Guzder-Williams, Tanya Birch, Samantha Brooks Hyde, Joseph Mazzariello, Wanda Czerwinski, Valerie J. Pasquarella, Robert Haertel, Simon Ilyushchenko, Kurt Schwehr, Mikaela Weisse, Fred Stolle, Craig Hanson, Oliver Guinan, Rebecca Moore, and Alexander M. Tait. 2022. "Dynamic World, Near Real-Time Global 10 m Land Use Land Cover Mapping." *Scientific Data* 9(1):251 [doi: 10.1038/s41597-022-01307-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01307-4), 2022

[10] Hu, Jie, Li Shen, Samuel Albanie, Gang Sun, . "Squeeze-and-ExcitationNetworks." [doi: 10.48550/arXiv](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv), 2019.

[11] Zhang, Hang, Chongruo Wu, Zhongyue Zhang, Yi Zhu, Haibin Lin, Zhi Zhang, Yue Sun, Tong He, Jonas Mueller, R. Manmatha, Mu Li, and Alexander Smola. 2020. "ResNeSt: Split-Attention Networks." [doi: 10.48550/arXiv](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv), 2020.

[12] Akiba, Takuya, Shotaro Sano, Toshihiko Yanase, Takeru Ohta, and Masanori Koyama. 2019. "Optuna: A Next-Generation Hyperparameter Optimization Framework." [doi: 10.48550/arXiv](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv), 2019